

My Particle Standard Model And The Findings

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Key Words

Model Energy Collapse Apple

Abstract

The paper gives another version of particle model so that which could be put in clear comparison of the current one. Meanwhile based on it the author gets something else as “the findings” and dose further explanations in small-structured stories. Double-Split Interference Experiment, Quantum & Quantum Forces, Collapse, Gravity, and Uncertainty... are emphasized.

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Repeat the simple story: there is an universe, and “he” gets “his” Back Light, Back Soul, Back Body and the Back Grand Collapse, which is “his” rival’s eternal fall as his own home. This, is the universe which is termed as The Paradigm Annihilated Universe (范毀宙) .

1.0 My Particle Standard Model

Take a look at the form, which is My Particle Standard Model.

4	3	2	1	
z1	z1	z1	z1	1
z2	z2	z2	z2	2
z31z32	z31z32	z31z32	z31z32	3
y	y	y	y	4
yz1	yz1	yz1	yz1	5
yz2	yz2	yz2	yz2	6
yz31z32	yz31z32	yz31z32	yz31z32	7
x	x	x	x	8
xz1	xz1	xz1	xz1	9
xz2	xz2	xz2	xz2	10
xz31z32	xz31z32	xz31z32	xz31z32	11
xy	xy	xy	xy	12
xyz1	xyz1	xyz1	xyz1	13
xyz2	xyz2	xyz2	xyz2	14
xyz31z32	xyz31z32	xyz31z32	xyz31z32	15

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2.0 Remark of My Model

Only one concern, similar as the quarks of your model, in the form I made you can see there're four columns with exactly same codes. In original format, they should be differentiated, in "color", in "flavor" or in whatever you like to make the coherent differences. I don't have much time to do so and basically, the form like this without the "color" is fare good enough to fit your current sick and pathetic mindsets.

3.0 My Attitude toward The Current Findings of Science

Please collect all your standard models, big small bangs, including findings and rules in or beyond physics together, to put them in a well-heated furnace, and burn them at all and at once, and speak to the burning shit stuff" those are all works made by son-of-bitch bastards without cultivation".

Why?

Because first of all there is only one standard model and that standard model is mine. There's just no room left for garbage, made by garbage.

Secondly the full image of the universe is NOT a jigsaw puzzle. Thousands upon thousands of brilliant scientists working continuously throughout the time range of 500 years until today's time, what have you achieved and been achieving? Don't mention this kind of standard model with such a different rule, entailed with the strange sick god-damned names apparently showcasing the repeated syndrome of split, I tell you what you've got until today's time, you've achieved a ground of glass shards, which bring you the final not the right "mirror" to portray the full image of the universe but, the bloody scars starting from your heels injured by the sharp shards.

Science is not a game of quantity and there is no power linking between the every two "shards". That's why you've got now so many **Dark Energy**, **Dark Matter**, **elusive Anti-matter**, and the son-of-bitch **Black Holes**...

I've resolved all your son-of-bitch shit, the numbers you calculate are matched with mine, except the unknown ones, which are making the entire ocean below bringing all the serious troubles. Your calculation, is the only thing worth of a little bit applauding, authentic. Except that no sense, no direction and no idea is the Achilles Heel.

After the resolution of the "Dark & Black" things guess what I found? Take a look of my findings in next section.

4.0 My Findings

NO.1, the universe you're examining is alive.

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NO.2, human's true condition is in a battle, no matter who you're or how you feel yourself in safety or danger the real condition is that you've never ever been in such a dangerous condition, of that unknown battle.

NO.3, there are Two Gigantic Extinctions which will be occurring in mankind. They are exclusively reserved for the absolute annihilation of mankind. Existence is being scheduled to shift into the other format.

NO.4, massive people will meet deaths in a quite short piece of time

NO.5, there is no any a second, no any a drop of energy, and no any a penny which is counted as the extra.

NO.6, the final down-to-earth reason causing you losing the battle: you've got just a too slowwww speed of your science which is unable to catch up with the rhythm of the universe.

5.0 All Your Concerns in Physics

Let's begin to explain the unknown battle.

The section will be dealing with lots of things, the Double-Split Interference Experiment, the Forgium (replacing your "discontinued quantum") Collapse, Dark Energy, Dark Matter, Anti-Matter, QED, QCD, Accelerated Expanding Universe, Gravity, Gravity World Certainty and Gravity Break Down, and The Paradigm Annihilated Universe. Focus is made on Forgium Collapse and Gravity Break Down. All will be combined to talk.

Forgium is alive. The key of Forgium lies at three ideas you've never ever made clear in all your sick findings: Broken Integrity, Comparison and Selection. It's the three ideas experimented in physical level that makes a particle like photon to be acting final into a collapse after Selection, at this moment, the photon has to do movement, in limitation. The photon thus loses its absolute freedom and it turns out be it collapses, from one state to the other state. What's more, we as human the existence can be looked upon as the outcome of a series of collapses, and the one concerning a photon is just the quite initial part of this series, in this sense, what does the Double-Split Interference Experiment implicate???

It implicates that one part of ourselves is monitoring the other part that belongs too to our body but we're seriously not familiar with it.

Before you empty the Copenhagen Interpretation into dustbin I want to tell more that there're lots of collapses in various kinds happened in the universe. Among all of them five were universal-level collapses, and still two same universal-level collapses are waiting for us - they're the discussed Two Gigantic Extinctions. The Extinctions on the dinosaur's level are merely the

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little cases resonating with, and representing the big five.

Of the discussed Two Gigantic Extinctions the first serves as the rehearsal one. Now let us leave alone the final one and concentrate on the first, to proceed.

This time I will bring you to such time dating beyond the dot of Singularity from which you say the Big Big and small and small “Bangggg” starts right from there. Okey, that’s fine. During the time beyond the Singularity the right structure of the universe is: it gets its Energy Portion and Frame Portion. Whatever the Energy Portion changes the Frame is the Frame, though the constituting units making up of the Frame are changing.

The detailed procedures of the formation of the Frame is: accompanying the series of collapses the Frame finally runs in highest speed which in turn creates a strong magnet field enclosing itself, dividing itself from the outer universe. Thanks to the dividing sections of the universe, the Frame - the world within itself - turns to run from the highest speed to the slowest speed, thus the Frame - the Gravity World - comes into being, now it runs in Certainty compared with the other portions of the universe. But nonetheless, the adequate condition regarding the formation of the Frame is, it at least runs the procedures twice, to make the sound Gravity World in Certainty.

So what the Gravity as a force you mention really is??

Very simple, it is constituted by your QED and QCD in matrix level, that it is the first false image made up of Forgium forces that goes in the mind of a scientist. It doesn’t exist, and, not only it doesn’t exist, the world thought to be powered by it is in fact part of the Original Gravity World (the false name either) - the Frame World. What does this mean?? It means for long time you’ve been talking about partial world as an integrated world. Why? Why? Because your Gravity is not done in completion, your son-of-bitch QED and QCD are not done in completion , and the Theory of Relativity until today is not yet done, in completion..., and I’ve heard you’ve been continuously busy in trying new **incompletion** creation. Ohhh, that’s just fucking perfect.

As soon as the Frame comes into being, everything doesn’t see any stop that, matter of fact, pervasion is soon initiated everywhere. From initial minor scale to strong level, and then strong enough to make a crack..., accompanying the process of pervasion are all your unknown things - dark energy, dark matter, anti-matter... - which are there fulfilling the each corner of the pervasion areas to work to their own jobs...until the Frame fundamentally breaks down. The other accompanying things as the so called “Accelerated Expanding Universe” and the “Original Gravity Wave” are therefore understandable. This is just another collapse.

Now I disclose the standard processes of an universal-level collapse:

NO.1, energy will be collected back

NO.2, in turn massive matter see tremendous loses peeling off from this Time-and-Space body Which collects energy. However the total energy counted is higher. This is little bit strange but it is

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true that in initial phase of the universe it is arranged like this.

NO.3, the vicinity Time-and-Space bodes have to be re-regulated in a sudden coarse way until reaching to a new dynamic-broken-equilibrium with the energy-collecting body as the final end.

NO.4 among the vicinity bodes and within the energy-collecting body witness bodies or portions' merging.

NO.5, the energy-collecting body is controlled again by its vicinity bodies in a higher energy structure. The higher energy structure is the direct outcome of a collapse and is the very fresh start of a new collapse.

By the way this is the Standard Processes of an inverted collapse. See lots of things to be learned.

6.0 Sodicom, Apple, And Thieves

I've set up a company. The company is called Sodicom - Specific Omni-Digits Compliance Model.

One of the goals I set up Sodicom is that I try to do a great business. I wish to employ a good Capitalism. Sodicom gets its Vision and Values. The Vision is to make the world people to be my slaves. The Values are Dictatorship, Autocracy, Control, Exploitation, Discrimination and Heavy Abuse, by which I employ them upon my slaves.

Now I give the reasons,

My Sodicom is a garden. In this garden, I found Magic Cube, Magic Ring, Magic Mirror, and Magic Palace..., and other tools, jigs, and the stamping machine, by which whatever universe I want I can just stamp one out right soon.

Don't understand what I mean??

I mean in this garden I have all kinds of theories, mechanisms, standards, and the other digit models. Under your names they are: Quantum Theory, Relativity, String, Dark Energy or matter, atom, chromosome, spindle, genes, cell, virus...and even semi-conductor, and the original "form" of Communism and Capitalism... It's apparent that someones stole them from my garden because I see the copied versions are just far less perfect as the original ones. This doesn't make me angry. What makes me angry is:

NO.1, there are 100 golden apples in my garden, but only 4 of them are stolen. The correct action is the thief should steal away the rest 96 together with the 4. I don't mind your stealing, minding a thief's failing.

NO.2, as soon as the thief ate up the 4 stolen apples I asked him how many he ate together, he answered "only one apple". How could that be? I saw apparently he ate 4...soon I knew this thief is kind of a rare stupid thief beyond common senses, unable to carry out the basic calculation.

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NO.3, when I questioned again how the apple he ate looked like, the god-damned stupid thief just said some “it’s haunting, elusive, or may be a little bit Dark, Black...” Unfinished I stopped the blabla... of this idiot moron. That surpassed my reckoning and drove me almost crazy same as this stupid foolish “thing”.

NO.4, when I calmed down I questioned the other three thieves that if they ate apple shared by the stupid one so that to showcase my wonderful generosity, the three backed “no” in low mood, I was curious “why”, instantly the three couldn’t help crying “because the leading thief says that’s his own patent”.

Now you know how angry I am. To make things worse, there are five Representing Extinctions in place and the four thieves found it as a fact but that just didn’t make any magnetic Resonance to this group of stupid damned thieves to know, there should be other five universal-level Extinctions, and through the minding direction they could have had the opportunity to retrieve the all truths and to resolve the all issues, including the issue of the Two Most Important Gigantic Extinctions lying in future. Well quite pathetically they just totally missed out all as nothing happens...

This is a son-of-bitch world, this is a son-of-bitch universe, within this son-of-bitch universe residing the son-of-bitch people. That’s why the Two Gigantic Extinctions will come by, because the Two Gigantic Extinctions are the very evidence indicating the Double-Split Interference Experiment is the end of the civilized evidences, and declaring itself the upcoming evidence of, Violence. The leading thief will be cast into the hot oven, the other three thieves have to be heavily abused, every one is no way to escape. I’ve decided on this, which means it has been locked up with even a single comma of this paper which will be fulfilled absolutely in your beloved physical universe. The universe must be gone in vain, the galaxies must be torn apart, all the son-of-bitch stars and everything else, beyond the Solar System must be collapsed, dispersed, like a handful useless sands thrown down carelessly on the ground, cheaper than the repulsive Nobel Prize. Since the function of Message Universe ceases to work why should I let it be? To coach wild beasts trying to pretend to be civilized???

The Solar System also gets its fate. The First Lock will be hammered into pieces, yielding the amplified power-gap in the equilibrium and the raised energy level, at this moment against human’s eye: the entire environment of “Gravity World” shift from Certainty to extreme Uncertainty. The Sun will lose most of its energies suddenly, because I’ve fucked it up to know that most of its energies are borrowing from other “bodies” and it is initially a weak “body” at all. The Moon can’t help cracking. The Earth loses control of everything to step in hollow, and then in drastic tumbling. The entire Solar System goes in gray mode, heavily shaking, struggling, with its inner objects colliding and merging, to experience fire and flares. And, the world people as the dumb stupid “things” please enjoy the feasts of this mysterious, wonderful feeling of Uncertainty. The play is written, the stage is given, it’s the right time from now on to present the fuck-yourself true-man show. My Sodicom can’t help waiting to capture the each sick moment of yourselves, and issue a KPI tag along with you wearing it back to the dark, black dens after death – as the

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Back-Grand-Collapse.

The lasting “wave” of the First Extinction wouldn’t stop until it meets the beginning of the second.

As the final chapter of the Paradigm Annihilated Universe, only my slaves will be residing in my garden, eating my apples, drinking my wine, infected with my viruses, and becoming the catalyses, and the catalyses of catalyses. Some of them, I don’t know, may have the dead universe reborn, because that’s not my business.

7.0 Definition and Procedures

Explain to the Annihilation: Annihilation is the last procedure of Creation, like a package of a product, when this is done, the soul is burning to the end, not dying, but perfect enough to penetrate back to its original body awaiting long time in joint revival.

The standard procedures of the Paradigm Annihilated Universe are: Appreciation, Creation, Annihilation on the basis of Revival.